

PARACHOR OF ORTHOPHOSPHORIC ACID

BY V. G. VAIDYA AND B. K. MAHESHWARI

Vaidya and co-workers (*J. VK. Univ.* 1957, 1, 73 ; *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1956, 5-II) have studied parachor of nitric and sulphuric acids and have established intramolecular hydrogen bonds in them. A similar study of orthophosphoric acid of strengths 15.87 M to 2.55 M has been undertaken. The results are shown below.

TABLE I

Conc.	Temp.	α .	M_m .	d .	P_m .	P_r .	
15.87 M	21.6°	0.5977	65.811	1.747	82.87	113.70	154.7
14.71	22.2°	0.5069	58.546	1.698	81.70	103.60	153.2
13.61	21.0°	0.4358	52.870	1.651	79.52	95.61	151.3
13.03	23.0°	0.4017	50.130	1.628	80.19	92.19	151.1
12.00	21.7°	0.3490	45.920	1.580	81.02	87.20	151.7
11.03	18.9°	0.3026	42.200	1.538	80.19	82.12	150.3
10.27	23.6°	0.2714	39.710	1.502	80.69	79.25	150.8
9.40	23.0°	0.2388	37.110	1.462	79.23	75.75	149.6
8.55	22.0°	0.2085	34.690	1.422	78.96	72.68	148.9
7.50	21.5°	0.1748	31.990	1.373	75.91	68.79	145.2
6.79	20.6°	0.1537	30.300	1.340	76.15	66.80	145.0
6.16	21.7°	0.1361	28.890	1.309	75.78	65.13	144.7
2.55	25.8°	0.0435	21.482	1.114	74.20	56.59	144.4

The value of parachor for strongest solution of the acid is found to be 154.7. Arbutov and Vinogradova (*Izvest Akad. Nauk, SSSR, Otdel Khim. Nauk*, 1951, 733) have found the parachor of esters of phosphoric acid and Vogel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1804) that of orthophosphate group. The parachor of orthophosphoric acid calculated indirectly from their values is 155.16 which closely agrees with the value obtained by us. The parachor calculated for the acid is 167.6, showing a drop of 13 units in the observed value. Several communications from this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 53, 62 ; 1952, 29, 679) show that there is a parachor drop due to ionisation and hydrogen bonding. Nims (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 1946 ; 1934, 56, 1110) has found the values for K_1 and K_2 of the acid to be 8.95×10^{-3} and 6.056×10^{-3} respectively. Smith ("Analytical Processes—A Physico-chemical Interpretation", 1949, p. 445) records the value of K_2 to be 4.8×10^{-3} . It is therefore quite obvious that there is very little ionisation in the strongest acid. Therefore, the parachor drop can be ascribed to hydrogen bonding only. The acid can therefore be represented as:

Venkateswaran (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1938, 7A, 13) from the study of Raman spectra of disodium hydrogen phosphate has found the presence of a hydrogen bond in the compound. Hendricks (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1927, 14, 269) and West (*Z. Krist.*, 1930, 74, 306) have established the presence of hydrogen bonds in potassium dihydrogen phosphate crystals from crystallographic studies. It is thus reasonable to assume that two intramolecular hydrogen bonds exist in the orthophosphoric acid molecule. Our results confirm this.

The value of parachor drops from 154.7 at 15.87 *M* to 144.4 at 2.55 *M*. This drop is due to gradual and regular ionisation.

The authors wish to thank Dr. S. N. Kaveeshwar for his valuable suggestions and keen interest in the work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
HOLEKAR COLLEGE, INDORE.

Received May 3, 1957.